

Examining the research taxonomy of poverty in SAARC countries (2013-2022): A Scientometrics analysis using R package and VOS

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Abstract

South Asia risks having large pockets of persistent poverty. SAARC countries have seen an enormous amount of literature on the area of poverty. Using the R package and VOS viewer programme, this study aims to conduct Scientometric analysis in order to derive a graphical mapping of the bibliographic data for poverty-related publications in the SAARC region. The results showed that the number of publications since 2013 is in an upward mode, but shows a downward move around 2015. However, from 2019 onwards, the number of publications has witnessed a rising mode. In the country-wise publication, India ranked at the top.

Keywords: Poverty, Visualisation of Similarities, R Package, SAARC, Scientometrics analysis

1. Introduction

Poverty has been a fact of life for millennia, preventing people from living comfortably by

depriving them of food, clothing, shelter, nutrition, and other resources/opportunities. It causes social inequity and class conflict (Cazacu & Crudu, 2019). Though it is widely portrayed as a widespread phenomenon in third-world countries, it is also a serious issue and

cause for concern in the world's richest and most developed countries (Bertolini, 2019).

The World Bank has set an ambitious target of eliminating extreme poverty worldwide by 2030 (Lakner et al,2022). To guide its work, the World Bank established two goals: the first is to eradicate extreme poverty by 2030, and the second is to promote shared prosperity. The first goal will be met if the incidence of extreme poverty falls below 3% by 2030, while the second goal can be met by increasing the average welfare of those in each country earning at or below the 40th percentile (Jolliffe,2014). Resources must be directed toward countries with the highest rates of extreme poverty in order to achieve the first goal. The extreme poor are most

concentrated in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia (World Bank,2020). Extreme poverty affects 12.6 percent of the global population, or one in every eight people. With 50.7 percent and 33.4 percent of the world's extreme poor, respectively, Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia have the highest and second-highest proportions of the world's extreme poor (Islam et al,2021).

Poverty is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that affects millions of people worldwide, including South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation members. The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation is abbreviated as SAARC. It is an intergovernmental organisation made up of eight South Asian countries: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, the Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. SAARC was established in 1985 with the goal of fostering regional cooperation in areas such as trade, economics, culture, and politics. SAARC countries have witnessed progress in the economic sphere. But poverty still remains as one of the significant challenges in the region affecting the health, education and social well-being of many people in this region. The covid 19 pandemic has aggravated the poverty situation in the region. It has widened income disparities, depleted human capital, and negatively impacted education and health outcomes for millions of vulnerable people. Nearly two-thirds of those who fell or remained in extreme poverty as a result of the pandemic live in South Asia (Rasul et al,2021). Because of this, poverty alleviation has become one of the top priorities for the governments and international organizations in the SAARC countries.

Over the past decade, considerable research efforts have been devoted to understanding the different aspects of poverty in the SAARC region. Researchers have explored poverty's causes, consequences, and solutions, focusing on issues such as income inequality, health outcomes, education, and social welfare programs. However, since the field of research is diverse and vast, it is not an easy task to get a comprehensive understanding of the research trends and gaps.

The authors have selected Scientometric analysis as the best method to bridge the aforementioned research gaps and make a quantitative study of poverty-related publications in the SAARC region.

Scientometric is a field of study in the library and information science (LIS) that uses a wide variety of techniques and methods to make the quantitative study of research articles and other academic documents. Scientometric procedures depend upon information technology to analyse, process and prepare significant concepts. The word Scientometric was coined by Pritchard (1969), who defined it as follows: "To shed light on the process of written communication and of the nature and course of a discipline (in so far as this is displayed through written communication), by means of counting and analysing the various facets of written communication" (Pritchard,1969). The Scientometric analysis employs a systematic, explicit, and uniform evaluation procedure to report research contributions in a subject domain.

This study serves as a reference for any researcher with an interest in the field of poverty and provides an up-to-date summary of the research literature to promote a better grasp of the principles of poverty. The methodology used in the current study gives the researchers insights into the patterns and trends in scholarly publications on poverty originating in SAARC countries. Understanding current research trends and gaps in the region's poverty research is critical for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers to design and implement effective poverty reduction policies and programmes. By analysing the frequency and distribution of keywords, authors, institutions, and citation patterns, researchers can gain a better understanding of the key topics and themes about poverty in the SAARC region. Scientometric analysis can also help researchers to identify the most influential authors, institutions, and publications on poverty in the SAARC region. This can be useful in identifying potential collaborators, mentors, and sources of funding for research projects. This method will assist in identifying neglected research areas, under-researched regions, or topics that require additional attention. The findings will

serve as a foundation for future research in the region and will help to build a knowledge network that will aid in poverty reduction efforts. Scientometric analysis can help researchers to evaluate the impact of their own publications and research output in the domain of poverty in the SAARC region. By analysing citation patterns and co-authorship networks, researchers can gain insights into the visibility and influence of their research. Scientometric analysis can also help researchers to identify research gaps and areas of potential future research in the field of poverty in the SAARC region. By identifying areas of low publication output or areas where there is a high concentration of research, researchers can gain insights into where there may be opportunities for new research and innovation. The study's findings will contribute to a better understanding of the research landscape on poverty in the SAARC countries. This understanding will provide insights into the research gaps and help policymakers and practitioners identify the areas where research and knowledge transfer can make the most significant impact in reducing poverty.

This study provides the data analysis of the research literature on poverty in SAARC nations by utilising the R package bibliometrix and the Visualisation of Similarities (VOS) viewer tool.

2. Methodology

Scientometric analysis was used in this study to review the poverty literature by utilising the R package Scientometric and the Visualisation of Similarities (VOS) viewer tool. The methodology of this study involved several steps. The first step was data collection, where the Scopus database was selected, and relevant search terms were used to identify publications in the field of poverty. The next step was data screening, where the publications were screened to ensure that they met the inclusion criteria for the study. The third step was data analysis, where Scientometric techniques are used to analyse the collected data. This included analysing citation patterns, identifying influential authors and publications, identifying research trends in the field etc. Finally, the results of the analysis were interpreted and reported, providing insights into the

state of research in poverty and highlighting future research directions

2.1 Data collection and search strategy

The study was conducted using Scientometric analysis of the literature published on poverty by SAARC countries. Scopus database has been used to carry out the study over other databases such as Web of Science and Pubmed etc. The most important reason to select the Scopus database for this study is that more publications are available in the Scopus database than in Web of Science, Pubmed etc (Anglada-Tort & Sanfilippo, 2019). The data were refined in various parameters in order to meet the objectives of the study. Firstly, in the Scopus database search engine the string (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Poverty")) was used to extract the data. The search result showed 1,72,684 documents. Secondly, the scholars delimited the study from 2013-2022 as it is difficult to conduct the study with a large number of documents. After delimiting the search for a specific duration, 91,666 documents were remaining. Thirdly, in terms of Subject Area, the study was limited to Social Science and multi-disciplinary. The fourth step in the process was to refine the search by document type. The search was refined to articles and all the other documents such as Book chapters, reviews, conference papers, books etc were removed. After that, the remaining documents were 29,482. Fifthly the search was refined by the publication stage. The finally published documents were considered for the study and the articles in the press were not considered. After this, the number of documents came down to 28,793. The sixth step was the most important. The search was refined to only Eight SAARC countries. The documents published in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Mauritius, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka were selected leaving all the other countries. After the search was limited to SAARC countries, the number of documents drastically reduced to 1,968 from 28,793. The final step in the search refinement involved language. Despite the fact that such studies involved publication of a variety of languages, this study has only chosen those articles that were written in the English language because it is the universal language

of communication. In the end, 1,967 articles were chosen for the analysis. The final set of articles was retrieved from the Scopus database, and analysis was carried out using VoS and R software. An approach similar to that recommended by Cancino et al. (2019) and Colares et al. (2020) was utilised to analyse the obtained data using the VOSviewer. Additionally, Scientometric analysis has been applied to this study using the R package, as suggested by Luo et al. (2018) and Anglada-Tort and Sanfilippo (2019).

The Scopus dataset for the study had 5370 authors and 1967 unique documents on the defined topic. Using an overview of the dataset, the authors have classified their findings using 4518 different keywords. Additionally, each work received an average of 10.16 citations. According to this conclusion, few articles have a significant number of citations, while many articles have few or no citations. The dataset also contained 396 articles on poverty that were solely written by a single author, while the average number of co-authors per manuscript was 3.52, which shows that attempts at collaborative study frequently result in research on poverty in SAARC countries. Table 1 displays this data's statistics.

3. Data analysis and visualisation

Table 1

Summary of the Scientometric Statistics of Poverty related publications

Description	Results
Timespan	2013:2022
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	586
Documents	1967
Annual Growth Rate %	8.14
Document Average Age	4.9
Average citations per doc	10.16
References	84852
Keywords Plus (ID)	4361

Author's Keywords (DE)	4518
Authors	5370
Authors of single-authored docs	349
Single-authored docs	396
Co-Authors per Doc	3.52
International co-authorships %	42.2

Fig. 1 Annual scientific production of poverty-related publications indexed in SCOPUS, 2013–2022

Poverty publications from 2013 to 2022 are distributed across the board in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1, the growth in research on poverty in SAARC countries publications slightly fluctuated especially, between 2013 to 2019, but shows a stable increased growth from the year 2019 to 2022. The year 2022 has the highest number of publications in the field with 269 articles, followed by 266 articles in 2021 and 257 articles in 2020. The findings, as shown in this table, demonstrate the rising interest that academics have each year in the topic of poverty in SAARC countries.

Fig. 2

The top publishing countries on poverty in SAARC Countries by scholars

According to the total number of publications on poverty in SAARC countries by scholars, counted for each author’s country, the top publishing countries are shown in Fig. 2. In terms of publishing articles on poverty, India leads a group of 112 nations, followed by Bangladesh, Pakistan, the United States and the United Kingdom. The analysis also shows that other nations like Australia, Nepal, China, Canada, Malaysia, Germany, and Sri Lanka have made efforts to advance research in the field of public relations.

Fig 3

Corresponding Author's Country representing inter-country (MCP) collaboration and intra-country (SCP) collaboration

Table 2

Analysis of Single Country Publications and Multiple Country Publications

Country	Articles	SCP	MCP	Freq	MCP_Ratio
INDIA	637	561	76	0.324	0.119
PAKISTAN	148	99	49	0.075	0.331
BANGLADESH	146	82	64	0.074	0.438
USA	91	5	86	0.046	0.945
UNITED KINGDOM	89	6	83	0.045	0.933
AUSTRALIA	52	5	47	0.026	0.904
CHINA	44	1	43	0.022	0.977
NEPAL	32	22	10	0.016	0.313
MALAYSIA	28	0	28	0.014	1
SRI LANKA	19	13	6	0.01	0.316

This study also looked at publishing output in relation to the countries of the corresponding authors, as well as active participation in poverty research in SAARC countries. As shown in Table 2 and Figure 3, India tops the list with 637, 561 single-country publications, 76 multi-country publications, and the highest frequency, 0.324. In SAARC countries, India ranks first in terms of poverty-related publications.

Fig. 4 Country Collaboration Map

Table 3

Country Collaboration ranking and frequency

Rank	From	To	Freq
1	INDIA	USA	137
2	INDIA	UNITED KINGDOM	97
3	BANGLADESH	UNITED KINGDOM	50
3	BANGLADESH	USA	50
4	BANGLADESH	AUSTRALIA	47
5	INDIA	AUSTRALIA	44

6	PAKISTAN	CHINA	42
7	USA	UNITED KINGDOM	37
8	BANGLADESH	MALAYSIA	26
9	PAKISTAN	USA	26
10	INDIA	CANADA	24

Figure 4 depicts the SAARC country collaboration map on poverty. There are 2872 collaboration entries from various countries around the world, with a maximum of 137 to one collaboration. Table 3 shows the ranking and frequency of countries that collaborate. According to the table, India and the United States of America have the most collaborations with 137, followed by India and the United Kingdom with 97, Bangladesh and the United Kingdom and Bangladesh and the United States of America with 50 each, Bangladesh and Australia with 47, India and Australia with 44, and Pakistan and China with 42. Figure 4 also shows an interesting revelation of Bangladesh's collaboration with the United Kingdom and the United States of America ranking and sharing the same frequencies.

Table 4

Top 20 cited documents published on poverty in SAARC Countries

Sl. No.	Authors	Title	Year	Global Citation	Local citation	TC/Y
1	Rockström J., Williams J., Daily G., Noble A., Matthews N., Gordon L., Wetterstrand H., DeClerck F., Shah M., Steduto P., de Fraiture C., Hatibu N., Unver O., Bird J., Sibanda L., Smith J.	Sustainable intensification of agriculture for human prosperity and global sustainability	2017	512	1	46.429

2	Ali A., Erenstein O.	Assessing farmer use of climate change adaptation practices and impacts on food security and poverty in Pakistan	2017	285	3	38.5
3	Corburn J., Vlahov D., Mberu B., Riley L., Caiaffa W.T., Rashid S.F., Ko A., Patel S., Jukur S., Martínez-Herrera E., Jayasinghe S., Agarwal S., Nguendo-Yongsi B., Weru J., Ouma S., Edmundo K., Oni T., Ayad H.	Slum Health: Arresting COVID-19 and Improving Well-Being in Urban Informal Settlements	2020	283	0	16.889
4	Spears D., Ghosh A., Cumming O.	Open Defecation and Childhood Stunting in India: An Ecological Analysis of New Data from 112 Districts	2013	212	2	11.333
5	Li W., Chien F., Hsu C.-C., Zhang Y., Nawaz M.A., Iqbal S., Mohsin M.	Nexus between energy poverty and energy efficiency: Estimating the long-run dynamics	2021	175	1	14.5

6	Hanlon C., Luitel N.P., Kathree T., Murhar V., Shrivasta S., Medhin G., Ssebunnya J., Fekadu A., Shidhaye R., Petersen I., Jordans M., Kigozi F., Thornicroft G., Patel V., Tomlinson M., Lund C., Breuer E., De Silva M., Prince M.	Challenges and opportunities for implementing integrated mental health care: A district level situation analysis from five low- and middle-income countries	2014	175	0	7.4
7	Fisher J.A., Patenaude G., Giri K., Lewis K., Meir P., Pinho P., Rounsevell M.D.A., Williams M.	Understanding the relationships between ecosystem services and poverty alleviation: A conceptual framework	2014	169	1	6.7
8	Allouche J., Middleton C., Gyawali D.	Technical veil, hidden politics: Interrogating the power linkages behind the nexus	2015	167	0	5.9
9	Islam S.M.D.-U., Bodrud-Doza M., Khan R.M., Haque M.A., Mamun M.A.	Exploring COVID-19 stress and its factors in Bangladesh: A perception-based study	2020	155	0	6.556
10	Shammi M., Bodrud-Doza M., Towfiqul Islam A.R.M., Rahman M.M.	COVID-19 pandemic, socioeconomic crisis and human stress in resource-limited settings: A case from Bangladesh	2020	154	1	10

11	Nasir S.	Microfinance in India: Contemporary issues and challenges	2013	144	2	4.5
12	Vellakkal S., Subramanian S.V., Millett C., Basu S., Stuckler D., Ebrahim S.	Socioeconomic Inequalities in Non-Communicable Diseases Prevalence in India: Disparities between Self-Reported Diagnoses and Standardized Measures	2013	134	1	4
13	Walker R., Kyomuhendo G.B., Chase E., Choudhry S., Gubrium E.K., Nicola J.Y., Lodemel I., Mathew L., Mwiine A., Pellissery S., Ming Y.	Poverty in global perspective: Is shame a common denominator?	2013	127	1	10.75
14	Toufique K.A., Belton B.	Is Aquaculture Pro-Poor? Empirical Evidence of Impacts on Fish Consumption in Bangladesh	2014	118	3	4.444
15	Sarker B.K., Rahman M., Rahman T., Hossain J., Reichenbach L., Mitra D.K.	Reasons for preference of home delivery with traditional birth attendants (TBAs) in Rural Bangladesh: A qualitative exploration	2016	113	4	8

16	Leal Filho W., Tripathi S.K., Andrade Guerra J.B.S.O.D., Giné-Garriga R., Orlovic Lovren V., Willats J.	Using the sustainable development goals towards a better understanding of sustainability challenges	2019	109	0	8
17	Islam R., Walkerden G.	How bonding and bridging networks contribute to disaster resilience and recovery on the Bangladeshi coast	2014	109	0	3.1
18	Dar M.H., De Janvry A., Emerick K., Raitzer D., Sadoulet E.	Flood-tolerant rice reduces yield variability and raises expected yield, differentially benefitting socially disadvantaged groups	2013	104	1	5.8
19	Pattnaik I., Lahiri-Dutt K., Lockie S., Pritchard B.	The feminization of agriculture or the feminization of agrarian distress? Tracking the trajectory of women in agriculture in India	2018	101	0	9.667
20	Belal A.R., Cooper S.M., Khan N.A.	Corporate environmental responsibility and accountability: What chance in vulnerable Bangladesh?	2015	99	0	2.636

In this scientometric study, the citation analysis was used to examine the level of connectedness between pairs of nodes (articles) in the 1967-node network. Table 4 lists the top 20 publications in terms of the number of local citations. The term “local citation” refers to how many times an article has been referenced by other articles in the

1967-node network (Niknejad et al., 2021). The term “global citation”, in contrast, refers to all of the citations that the work has received on Scopus (Niknejad et al., 2021). A substantial difference between the global citations and local citations figures, as shown in Table 4, indicates that academics and scholars in other fields have taken note of research on poverty in SAARC countries. Additionally, as seen in Table 4, the sequence of publications based on local citations differs from the sequence of publications based on global citations. Based on findings of the top 20 most cited works, topics on poverty, sustainability, climate change, health care, socio-economic and inequalities, were carried out the most.

Fig. 5 Co-Citation of sources

Table 5

Top 10 source impact journals

SOURCE TITLE	Frequency
Plos One	178
Sustainability Switzerland	54
Journal Of Rural Development	47
Social Indicators Research	46

Economic And Political Weekly	43
Indian Journal Of Human Development	39
International Journal Of Social Economics	32
Pakistan Development Review	26
World Development	25
Social Science And Medicine	23
Quality And Quantity	21
International Journal Of Scientific And Technology Research	19

Table 5 displays the top 10 impact journals. “The term impact factor has gradually evolved to describe both journal and author impact. Journal impact factors generally involve relatively large populations of articles and citations (Garfield, E. (1999).” It is a metric used to evaluate the importance and influence of a scholarly journal. It is calculated by dividing the number of citations to articles published in the previous two years in the current year by the total number of articles published in those two years. As indicated in Table 5, *Plos One* has the highest impact factor with 178 frequencies, followed by *Sustainability Switzerland* (54), *Journal of Rural Development* (47), *Social Indicators Research* (46) and *Economic and Political Weekly* (43).

Fig. 6

Co-citation of authors for publications on poverty

In the area of poverty study in SAARC countries, Fig. 6 shows the co-citation of writers. Alkire, S. is one of the most mentioned authors in the field of

poverty because his/her publication is the most referenced piece with a total of 396 citations in the research on the subject. Ravallion, M comes in second place with the most co-citations (323 citations). The figure also displays the various clusters and their connections are depicted by means of varied colours.

Fig. 7

Bibliographic coupling of documents

The articles’ bibliographic coupling of documents and a colour-coded cluster indicator are shown in Fig. 7. Additionally, the network’s distance or proximity between studies indicates how closely the nodes and publications are related bibliographically. For instance, the proximity of the two articles means that they share a large number of references (Niknejad et al., 2021; Marchiori and Franco, 2019). The articles with a minimum of five citations were only considered in this study. Out of the 1967 documents, 547 related articles met the criteria. All of the publications’ total link strengths and citation counts were calculated using the VOSviewer software, and the articles with the highest total link strengths were selected. The publication with the most citations, as shown in Fig. 7, was Rockström J. (2017), with 512 citations and 14 total link strengths.

Fig. 8 Bibliographic coupling of countries

The bibliographic coupling of countries is depicted visually in Fig. 8, where each node denotes a country and its size denotes the number of publications in that country. India, the United States, the United Kingdom, Bangladesh and Pakistan are the top research-producing nations in the area of poverty which do not complement Fig. 2. The next analysis created by the VOSviewer software uses co-occurrence of the author's keywords to fully comprehend the top search terms for research on poverty in SAARC countries during the present study period (Niknejad et al., 2021).

Fig. 9 Co-occurrence of authors’ keywords.

Fig.9 displays an analysis created by the VOSviewer programme, which was a method of thoroughly comprehending the most popular keywords for poverty at the time this study was being conducted and looks at the co-occurrence of the author's keywords. As shown in Fig. 9, poverty, Pakistan, inequality, gender, development, economic growth, vulnerability, economic growth and climate change are leading in the keywords used most frequently.

This study used the R package bibliometrix to analyse the author keywords using Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA). The graphical analysis of categorical data could be conducted using the data analysis method known as MCA (Niknejad et al., 2021; Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017). The current study chose MCA since it can assist in identifying the topic organisation among a collection of authors' keywords. A category depiction of how frequently used keywords are applied together can be made using the MCA technique, where the keywords are clustered based on their proximity (Niknejad et al., 2021; Demiroz and Haase, 2019). For instance, two keywords can be grouped together if they appear in several publications at the same time (e.g., poverty and human) (Niknejad et al., 2021; Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

network map. In some cases, the labels are not displayed to prevent circle overlap. The circle's size depends on how often an item appears. The relationships between the phrases are defined by the lines, while the colour reflects the cluster to which the terms belong. The separation between the objects shows how strong the connections are. For instance, terms that are closer to one another have stronger links than terms that are more apart (Niknejad et al., 2021). As shown in Fig.10, the most commonly-occurring terms (large circles) are poverty, human, adult, male, poverty alleviation, middle-aged, young adult, socioeconomic, healthcare delivery and gender. The VOSviewer software classified the most frequently used phrases into four groups using bibliometric mapping. The red-coloured cluster formed a larger group compared to the other colours, i.e. blue, green, yellow and purple. The red cluster contains the terms focused on poverty with connections to countries and states with terms like Pakistan, and Jharkhand linking with terms such as poverty alleviation, rural area, education, gender, microfinance, livelihood, vulnerability, income distribution, and climate change apart from others. The green clusters consist of terms focused on humans and health, like human, health care delivery, rural population, public health, economics, maternal health service and awareness are found in this cluster. The blue cluster focuses on terms such as socioeconomics, nutrition, sanitation, malnutrition, water supply, infant, newborn and breastfeeding. The yellow cluster focuses on terms such as adult, male, middle-aged, risk factor, social status, educational status and population research. The purple cluster is sparsely spread across and keywords such as young adult, interview and marriage are found in this cluster.

Fig. 10 Network view map generated by VOSviewer

Fig. 10 shows a network view map of the terms that were taken from article titles and abstracts. The obtained words are identified by labels, as seen in the

Multiple Correspondence Analysis

The Biblioshiny for Bibliometrix Conceptual Structure tool uses MCA to generate a conceptual structure for the identified field and k-means clustering to find groups of documents that cover related topics (Ejaz et al., 2022). Multivariate categorical analysis (MCA) is a multivariate exploratory method for graphically and

mathematically analysing multivariate categorical data (Matute & Linsen, 2022). It examines the interconnectedness of a collection of categorical data in order to identify new latent variables or factors.

Fig. 11 Factorial map using a correspondence analysis of the most cited documents related to poverty-based research

Fig. 12 Topic dendrogram using correspondence analysis that shows the hierarchical relationship between the topics in the identified field.

Fig. 13 Conceptual structure map using correspondence analysis that integrates and correlates the knowledge of current studies on poverty

To interpret the results, the relative locations and distribution of dots along the dimensions are used; the closer the words displayed in Figures 11-13, the more comparable their distribution. In the academia, the use of MCA, a novel statistical method, is growing (Ejaz et al., 2022). This technique reduces the number of data dimensions, resulting in two-dimensional visualisations that highlight data similarities. In this study, the phrases that are more diffused and closer to the centre of the map correspond to research topics that have recently received more attention than those that are more uniformly distributed (Ejaz et al., 2022).

4. Discussion

Poverty is a global phenomenon and various domestic, regional, and international governments along with non-governmental institutions aim to alleviate it around the globe. For the past many decades, the collaborative and multilateral efforts initiated by these agencies have resulted in significant changes in the poverty rate across the world. But the COVID-19 pandemic has again affected the poverty alleviation measures. The poverty level has risen from 70 million to more than 700 million Sumner, A. et.al. (2020). According to the World Bank estimation, extreme poverty at the global level has reached from 8.4 per cent in 2019 to 9.3 per cent World Bank (2022). As the world was recovering from the impact of COVID-19 and the war between Russia and Ukraine has fuelled rising food and

energy prices. This has hindered the recovery of the world from poverty. By the end of 2022, as many as 685 million people could still be living in extreme poverty Raghav Aggarwal. (2022). The recent crisis has pushed the global goal of ending extreme poverty by 2030. According to the World Bank, a steep decline was witnessed in the poverty level till the 2019 pandemic. During the pandemic, and after the pandemic, the number of poor people living below \$ 1.90 has risen from 641.4 million (2019) to 713.8 million (2020). This suggests that the COVID-19 pandemic has hindered the efforts taken to reduce poverty. The crisis has not spared South Asian countries; the number of people living below the poverty line has significantly increased due to the pandemic. It will take many years to recover from the effect of the pandemic.

In line with many national, regional and international agencies, research scholars across the world have contributed their ideas to end poverty around the globe. In an effort to study the scholar's contribution towards ending poverty in SAARC countries, this study used Sciento-metric analysis. The study aims to understand the contribution of scholars from across the globe using Sciento-metric analysis methods. The data for the study was collected from the Scopus database. Sciento-metric analysis was conducted using VOS software and R software. The results showed that the number of publications since 2013 is in an upward mode 2013 is in an upward mode, but shows a downward move around 2015. However, from 2019 onwards, the number of publications has witnessed a rising mode. This suggests that the annual scientific production of poverty-related articles indexed in Scopus is in an oscillating mode. In the country-wise publication, India ranked top with 1186 articles followed by Bangladesh and Pakistan. In the top 20 most cited publications, articles were published on the topics of agriculture, food security and poverty in Pakistan, slum health, COVID-19, open defecation, starvation in India, energy poverty, mental health, poverty alleviation, microfinance in India, socioeconomic inequalities, non-communicable diseases, poverty, aquaculture, Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs), sustainable development goals, flood, agrarian distress and corporate environment responsibility etc. The article

titled “Sustainable Intensification of Agriculture for human prosperity and global sustainability” by Rockstrom J et.al.(2017) with 512 citations ranked top in the list. This article discussed sustainable intensification of agriculture (SIA), in which the authors proposed a paradigm shift toward sustainable intensification of agriculture, which integrates the dual and interdependent goals of using sustainable practises to meet rising human needs while also contributing to the resilience and sustainability of landscapes, the biosphere, and the Earth system. This article seeks to contribute to a more sustainable world within a safe operating environment on Earth. According to the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization, the use of fertiliser has increased from 52.27 million tonnes in 1961 to 213.77 million tonnes today, significantly deteriorating soil quality over time, as shown in Fig 14.

Fig. 14 Fertiliser consumption, 1961 to 2019

Pahalvi, Heena Nisar et.al. (2021) “suggest that continuous utilisation of chemical fertilisers is responsible for the decline of soil organic matter (SOM) content coupled with a decrease in the quality of agricultural soil. The overuse of chemical fertilisers hardens the soil, reduces soil fertility, pollutes air, water, and soil, and lessens important nutrients of soil and minerals, thereby bringing hazards to the environment.” The sustainability of agriculture is remaining in question due to the overuse of fertilisers. Instead of solving the problem of poverty, the consistent use of fertiliser aggravates the problem of poverty in the years ahead. The increase in the usage of fertiliser as shown in Fig. 14 reduces soil fertility thereby it creates more waste and

arid lands. In fact fertilisation of the soil results in the plant absorbing the fertiliser through the soil and they can enter into the food chain and create harmful effects on the human body Savci, S. (2012). So, in this way, the usage of fertilisers also causes severe health hazards. Hence, the top-cited article raised a very pertinent issue with regard to sustainable agriculture. In this context, the study plays a very crucial role in creating addition to the existing knowledge. The second most cited article was contributed by Ali A., Erenstein O (2017) titled "Assessing farmer use of climate change adaptation practices and impacts on food security and poverty in Pakistan" with 285 citations. The scholar assessed the factors influencing farmers' choice of climate change adaptation practises, as well as the associated impacts on household food security and poverty in Pakistan, in this article. Climate change adaptation practises at the farm level, in addition to reducing exposure to weather risks, can thus have significant development outcomes. In this study, one of the most significant aspects which have been dealt with is climate change and its greater impact on farmers' income. A lack of awareness about climate change adaptability practices will certainly decline the farmer's income. The recent study reiterates the findings that climate change will certainly have a negative impact on the farmer's income Kalli, R., & Jena, P. R., (2022). The third most cited article published on poverty was produced by Corburn J. et. al. (2020) titled "Slum health: arresting COVID-19 and improving well-being in urban informal settlements" with 283 citations. In this article scholars propose a detailed framework to save urban informal settlements from the COVID-19 pandemic spread by maintaining slum health. Poor people will be affected in many aspects such as lack of basic needs such as water, toilets, sewers, drainage, waste collection and secure and adequate housing.

Moreover, poverty is a multidimensional concept and in order to understand the concept, knowledge of many interrelated or associated concepts related to poverty needs to be appropriately understood. Similarly, in the top most cited articles, the concept of poverty is linked with many facets of poverty such as agriculture Rockström J., Williams J et. al. (2017), climate change Ali A. et. al. (2017), Jha S.K. (2017),

food security Rahman A. (2020), Choithani C. (2017), Sam A.S. et. al. (2019), Dar M.H. (2020), Ward F.A., (2013), urban sanitation McFarlane C. (2014), rural Aggarwal S. (2018), Eswaran M. (2013), Drèze J. (2013), deforestation Oldekop J.A. et. al. (2019), Shehzad K. et. al. (2014), changing landscape and flood hazard Adnan M.S.G. et. al. (2020), crop diversification, Birthal P.S. (2015), Anuja A.R.et. al. (2020), NREGA Salian P.V. (2014), Reimeingam M. (2016), Tripathy K.K. (2015), open defecation and childhood stunting Spears D. (2013), COVID-19 Islam S.M.D.-U (2020), Corburn J. (2020), Rai S.S. (2021), Microfinance and Inequality. Dutta A. (2018), Ali I. (2017), Sangwan S. (2020), Azad M.A.K (2016).

This is a scientometric study of 1967 articles extracted from the Scopus database contributed by 5370 scholars on the topic of poverty in all the SAARC countries published from 2013 to 2022. Out of the 1967 articles, 396 documents were by single authors and the remaining articles were published by multiple authors. Analysis of Single and multiple-country publications also emphasises that Single Country Publications are more than Multiple Country Publications. This is the same case with the top three publishing countries such as India with 637 (SCP-561, and MCP 76), Pakistan with 148 (SCP 99 and MCP-49) and Bangladesh with 146 (SCP -82, MCP – 64). The above analysis strongly suggests that the authors contributing to the poverty-related articles on poverty in SAARC countries need to take much effort to collaborate with other countries in order to understand the different dimensions of poverty. Although India's collaboration with the US (Table 3) is fairly good and India and other SAARC countries' collaboration with other countries requires special attention. The collaboration would help the SAARC countries to learn and execute the best policy practices from the other countries.

The VOS viewer software grouped the four groups of the most widely used phrases using bibliometric mapping. When compared to the other colours, which included blue, green, yellow, and purple, the red cluster formed a larger group. The red cluster contains terms that are concerned with eradicating poverty and have ties to specific nations and states, including Pakistan and Jharkhand, as well as terms

like poverty alleviation, rural areas, education, gender, microfinance, livelihood, vulnerability, income distribution, and climate change, among others. Human, health care delivery, rural population, public health, economics, maternal health service, and awareness are just a few of the terms found in the green clusters that are related to people and their health. The terms socioeconomics, nutrition, sanitation, malnutrition, water supply, infant, newborn, and nursing are the main topics of the blue cluster. The terms adult, male, middle-aged, risk factor, social position, educational status, and population study are highlighted in the yellow cluster. Keywords like young adult, interview, and marriage can be discovered in the sparsely distributed purple cluster. The analysis provides a summary of the literature included in the Scopus and displays the state of the SAARC countries' publication of research on poverty. The analysis indicates the overview of the literature published in the Scopus and shows the status of the poverty-related research publication in SAARC Countries.

Conclusion

The results of a scientometric analysis of 1967 articles on poverty that were published between 2013 and 2022 are presented in this study. The R package bibliometrix and the VOSviewer programme were used to carry out the current study. The results showed that the number of publications since 2013 is in an upward mode 2013 is in an upward mode, but shows a downward mode around 2015. However, from 2019 onwards, the number of publication has witnessed a rising mode. This suggests that the annual scientific production of poverty-related articles indexed in Scopus is in oscillating mode. In the country-wise publication, India ranked top with 1186 followed by Bangladesh and Pakistan. In the top 20 most cited publications, articles were published on agriculture, food security and poverty in Pakistan, slum health, COVID-19, open defecation, starvation in India, energy poverty, mental health, poverty alleviation, microfinance in India, Socioeconomic inequalities, non-communicable diseases, poverty, aquaculture, Traditional Birth Attendants, sustainable development goals, flood, agrarian distress and corporate environment responsibility etc. Analysis of Single and multiple-country publications also

emphasises that Single Country Publications are more than Multiple Country Publications. The network view map's results showed that poverty-related studies may be roughly divided into three main clusters and a few smaller clusters. The red, purple, and green clusters formed larger groupings than the orange, fluorescent green, light brown, and blue-coloured clusters. The red cluster contains terms that are concerned with eradicating poverty and have ties to specific nations and states, including Pakistan and Jharkhand, as well as terms like poverty alleviation, rural areas, education, gender, microfinance, livelihood, vulnerability, income distribution, and climate change, among others. Human, health care delivery, rural population, public health, economics, maternal health service, and awareness are just a few of the terms found in the green clusters that are related to people and their health. The terms socioeconomics, nutrition, sanitation, malnutrition, water supply, infant, newborn, and nursing are the main topics of the blue cluster. The terms adult, male, middle-aged, risk factor, social position, educational status, and population study are highlighted in the yellow cluster. Keywords like young adult, interview, and marriage can be discovered in the sparsely distributed purple cluster.

This study has its limits despite scientific achievements. Information was taken from the Scopus database. As a result, this study might have used the database's weaknesses. For instance, the Scopus database collects data using a full counting process. Due to this, articles with numerous co-authors usually have more analytical relevance than those with just one author. This study also included fractional counting to mapping analysis utilising the VOSviewer programme to address this problem. Co-citation, bibliographic coupling, and the co-occurrence of author keywords were all considered in the analysis. Similar findings were obtained using complete and fractional counting. The study's conclusions can therefore be trusted because there is no discernible difference between the two counting techniques. The outcomes of this study are dynamic and subject to change as poverty-related research expands significantly each year. As a result,

it is advised that this research be carried out again in the upcoming years.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

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